

A facile synthesis of 3-substituted benzofurans and indoles through a palladium-catalyzed domino carbopalladation/CH-activation/isomerization process[†]

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Abstract : Novel benzofurans **7** and indoles **8** have been prepared from **3** and **4** by a Pd-catalyzed mono-component three-fold domino carbopalladation/CH-activation/isomerization process and from **12** and **5** to give **8** by a two-component fourfold domino Sonogashira/carbopalladation/CH-activation/isomerization process.

Keywords : Domino reaction, furans, indoles, palladium, carbopalladation, Sonogashira reaction.

Introduction

One of the most challenging tasks in organic synthesis is the development of ecologically and economically beneficial procedures for the facile construction of complex molecular structures. In the past decades, the concept of domino reactions, as introduced by our group¹, has received great interest, since it opens up efficient routes to natural products, bioactive compounds as well as materials starting from rather simple building blocks. In this regard, palladium-catalyzed transformations have been favored as one of the most powerful C–C-bond-forming tools². However, one major drawback is the prerequisite for prefunctionalization of one or both coupling partners, whereas direct arylations via CH-activation represent a more appropriate strategy using readily available substrates³; a combination of the aforementioned concepts can lead to a dramatic enhancement of the synthetic potential by saving resources, time and money⁴.

The domino strategy has been employed by our group in the synthesis of several natural products, such as α -tocopherol, using an enantioselective domino Wacker/Heck-reaction⁵ or in the first total synthesis of (+)-

linoxepin by establishing a domino carbopalladation/Heck-reaction⁶. Moreover, we have applied an enantioselective domino Wacker/carbonylation/methoxylation reaction for the synthesis of (–)-diversonol⁷ and (–)-blennolide **A**⁸. Furthermore, oxazines⁹ and dioxanes¹⁰ have been prepared by this way. Finally, also helical tetra-substituted alkenes have been synthesized via domino-processes by us¹¹.

Here we describe a novel approach using Pd-catalyzed domino reactions towards benzofurans and indoles, which are important heterocyclic scaffolds in many natural products and bioactive compounds¹². In this respect, the development of facile and concise synthetic routes towards these heterocycles has been addressed by numerous researchers (Scheme 1)¹³.

Several attempts have been reported including transition-metal catalyzed procedures such as an oxidative CH bond functionalization utilizing anilines and *N*-aryl imines, respectively in the presence of ruthenium (Ackermann *et al.*)¹⁴ or palladium (Wei *et al.*)¹⁵. Lautens described a facile synthesis employing *ortho-gem*-dihalovinyl-anilines¹⁶. A convenient one-pot method for the preparation of substituted benzofurans via a Pd-catalyzed phenol

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Scheme 1. Selected synthetic strategies for a concise construction of the indole and benzofuran core.

formation/cyclization protocol starting from 2-chloroaryl alkynes was published by the Buchwald group¹⁷. In addition, a metal-free cyclization of *ortho*-hydroxystilbenes has been developed by Wirth *et al.* for the generation of 2-arylbenzofurans and 2-arylnaphthofurans mediated by hypervalent iodine reagents¹⁸.

In recent studies, we have been able to prepare tetra-substituted alkenes of type **2** from **1** using a domino carbopalladation/CH-activation process (Scheme 2)^{11b}. These structures are of great interest as molecular switches and motors^{11,19}. The compounds are thermally stable; how-

Scheme 2. Synthesis of helical alkenes **2** via a palladium-catalyzed domino carbopalladation/CH-activation reaction.

ever, by incorporation of a heteroatom such as oxygen or nitrogen in the side chain of the starting material an isomerization occurs under the reaction conditions after the ring closure to give novel benzofurans and indoles by a domino carbopalladation/CH-activation/isomerization process.

Results and discussion

Reaction of the alkynes **3a-d** containing an oxygen in

the side chain with Pd(OAc)₂, PPh₃ and potassium carbonate as base in DMF at 100 °C for 2 h under microwave irradiation led to the benzofurans **7a-d** in 40–67% yield. In a similar reaction substrates **4a-e** containing a NAc group in the side chain gave the indoles **8a-e** in 63–83% yield. The higher yields in preparing the indoles might be due to their higher aromatic stabilization energy compared to the benzofurans which would facilitate the isomerization as the last step²⁰. Thus, we assume that after the oxidative addition a carbopalladation would take place to give the vinyl palladium intermediate **5**, which could undergo a direct arylation by a CH-activation leading to **6**. The final step would then be a thermal [1,3]-proton shift to afford the desired benzofurans **7** and indoles **8** (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3. Proposed mechanism of the domino carbopalladation/CH-activation/isomerization process of **3** and **4** to give benzofurans **7** and indoles **8**.

All substrates which we have investigated led to the desired products. In some cases traces of alkene **6** could be observed depending on the reaction temperature which supports the proposed mechanism. A pronounced influence of the substituents in the starting materials on the yields of the reaction was not observed, though substrates with electron donating groups gave always slightly better results. In the reaction of the nitrogen containing substrates **4c-e** small amounts of the *N*-acetyl deprotected products were observed besides **8c-e**.

Table 1. Pd-catalyzed domino reaction of alkynes **3** and **4**

Entry	Subst.	R ¹	R ²	X	Prod. ^a (%) ^b
1	3a	H	H	O	7a (40)
2	3b	Me	H	O	7b (65)
3	3c	OMe	H	O	7c (67)
4	3d	F	H	O	7d (55)
5	4a	H	H	NAc	8a (80)
6	4b	Me	H	NAc	8b (83)
7	4c	F	H	NAc	8c (63) ^c
8	4d	Me	Ph	NAc	8d (76) ^c
9	4e	F	<i>t</i> -Bu	NAc	8e (79) ^c

^aReaction conditions : Pd(OAc)₂ (20 mol%), PPh₃ (1.0 equiv.), K₂CO₃ (5.0 equiv.), DMF, 100 °C, 2–4 h, MW; ^bYield of isolated product; ^cDeprotected indole (X = NH) formed in small amounts (<10%).

The synthesis of the needed starting materials **3** and **4** is rather simple and was performed from the phenols **9** and acetanilides **10**, respectively (Scheme 4). Treatment of **9** and **10** with propargylic bromide led to the corresponding alkynes **11** and **12**, which were submitted to a

Scheme 4. Two-step synthetic route leading to several precursors **3** and **4** for the domino reaction; reaction conditions : [a] propargylic bromide, K₂CO₃ or KOH, MeCN, 60 °C, 16 h; [b] **5**, Pd(PPh₃)₄, CuI, *n*-Bu₄NOAc, 1,4-dioxane, 60 °C, 0.5–1.5 h.

Sonogashira-reaction employing biarylethers of type **5** to produce **3a–d** and **4a–e** with good to excellent yields over two steps (Table 2).

For a further improvement of the efficiency of the described synthesis of the benzofurans and indoles we developed a Pd-catalyzed two-component fourfold domino process which incorporates the Sonogashira coupling into the sequence. Thus, treatment of a mixture of the substrates **12b** and **12c** with **5a** and **5c** using Pd(OAc)₂, PPh₃ and *n*-Bu₄NOAc gave the indoles **8b**, **8c** and **8e** with almost similar or even higher yields compared to the three-fold domino process.

Finally, we have also shown exemplarily for **8c** that the *N*-acetyl group can be hydrolyzed to give the free indoles. Thus, treatment of **8c** with KOH in THF/H₂O at

40 °C led to the corresponding indole (**15**) in 94% yield.

Fig. 1 shows the crystal structure of indole **8b** in its lowest energy conformation, which can probably be traced back to minimal interactions between the xantheno group and the upper indole moiety. However, the barrier of rotation about the central CC-single bond with 19.89 kJ/mol, found by DFT calculations, is not very pronounced; for the substituted compound **8e** with a barrier of 20.47 kJ/mol.

In conclusion, we have developed a domino carbopalladation/CH-activation/isomerization and a domino Sonogashira/carbopalladation/CH-activation/isomerization process for the synthesis of novel benzofurans and indoles.

Experimental

Experimental methods : All air-sensitive reactions were performed under an argon atmosphere in flame-dried flasks and the reactants were introduced by syringe or transfer

Table 2. Synthesis of precursors **3a–d** and **4a–e** for the domino reaction

Entry	Subst.	R ¹	ArI (R ²)	X	Prod. ^a (%) ^b
1	9a	H	5a (H)	O	3a (quant.)
2	9b	Me	5a (H)	O	3b (98)
3	9c	OMe	5a (H)	O	3c ^c (77)
4	9d	F	5a (H)	O	3d ^c (94)
5	10a	H	5a (H)	NAc	4a ^{c,d} (75)
6	10b	Me	5a (H)	NAc	4b ^d (94)
7	10c	F	5a (H)	NAc	4c ^d (77)
8	10b	Me	5b (Ph)	NAc	4d ^d (94)
9	10c	F	5c (<i>t</i> -Bu)	NAc	4e ^d (79)

^aYield of isolated products over two steps; reaction conditions : ^bpropargylic bromide, K₂CO₃, MeCN, 60 °C, 16 h; **5**, Pd(PPh₃)₄, CuI, *n*-Bu₄NOAc, 1,4-dioxane, 60 °C, 0.5–1.5 h; ^cPdCl₂(PPh₃)₂ was used as catalyst; ^dKOH and BnEt₃NCl in THF were used as base.

Scheme 5. Domino Sonogashira/carbopalladation/CH-activation/isomerization process of **12b** and **12c** with **5a** and **5c** to give the indoles **8b**, **8c** and **8e**.

Fig. 1. Crystal structure of indole **8b**; depicted are the corresponding anisotropic displacement parameters at the 50% probability level.

cannula. All solvents were dried by standard methods and the reagents obtained from commercial sources were used without further purification. Thin-layer chromatography was performed on precoated silica gel plates (SIL G/UV₂₅₄, Machery-Nagel GmbH & Co. Kg). Silica gel 60 (0.032–0.064 mm, Merck) was used for column chromatography. Flash column chromatography was performed using the Isolera™ One flash purification system by Biotage with prepacked silica cartridges (SNAP 10, 25, 50, 100g).

NMR spectroscopy : NMR spectra were recorded with a Varian Mercury-300, Unity-300, Inova-500 and Inova-600 spectrometer and a Bruker AMX-300 spectrometer in CDCl₃; chemical shifts are given in ppm relative to tetramethylsilane (TMS), coupling constants *J* in Hertz. The solvent signals were used as references and the chemical shifts converted to the TMS scale (CHCl₃ : δ_H = 7.24 ppm, δ_C = 77.36 ppm). The multiplicities of first order were assigned as : s (singlet), s_{br} (broad singlet), d

(doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), dd (doublet of doublets), etc. Signals of higher orders were assigned as m (multiplet) respectively m_c (centered multiplet).

IR spectroscopy : IR spectra were recorded with a JASCO FT/IR-4100 spectrometer. All substances were applied neat on an ATR unit.

UV spectroscopy : UV spectra were recorded with a JASCO V-630 spectrometer.

Mass spectrometry : ESI MS and ESI HRMS spectra were recorded with a Bruker Daltonik Apex IV, EI MS and EI HRMS spectra were recorded with a Thermo Finnigan MAT 95.

Microwave reactor : Reactions of Microwave assisted syntheses were performed in a Smith Creator by Personal Chemistry and the Initiator™ 2.5 by Biotage (absorption level : very high) with the corresponding pressure vials.

The following abbreviations were used : aq. (aqueous), DMF (dimethylformamide), EtOAc (ethyl acetate), MTBE (methyl *tert*-butyl ether), PE (petroleum ether, b.p. = 40–60 °C), r.t. (room temperature), sat. (saturated), CC (column chromatography).

GP1 : General procedure for the Pd-catalyzed Sonogashira reaction :

A solution of aryl iodide **5** (1.00 equiv.), alkyne **11** or **12** (1.20 equiv.), Pd(PPh₃)₄ (0.05 equiv.), CuI (0.10 equiv.) and *n*-Bu₄NOAc (2.50 equiv.) in 1,4-dioxane (4–9 mL/mmol) was stirred for 0.5–2 h in a preheated oil bath at 60 °C. The reaction was allowed to reach r.t., the solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue was purified by CC to give **3** or **4**.

GP2 : General procedure for the Pd-catalyzed domino reaction :

Pd(OAc)₂ (0.20 equiv.) was added to a thoroughly degassed solution of alkyne **3** or **4** (1.00 equiv.), PPh₃

(1.00 equiv.) and K_2CO_3 (5.00 equiv.) in DMF (19–35 mL/mmol) and stirred under microwave irradiation for 2–4 h at 100 °C. The reaction was finished by the addition of sat. aq. NH_4Cl solution and H_2O . The aqueous layer was extracted with MTBE, the combined organic extracts were dried over $MgSO_4$, filtered and the solvent was removed *in vacuo*. The residue was purified by CC to give **7** or **8**.

GP3 : General procedure for the Pd-catalyzed intermolecular domino reaction of alkyne and aryl iodide :

$Pd(OAc)_2$ (0.20 equiv.) was added to a thoroughly degassed solution of aryl iodide **5** (1.20 equiv.), alkyne **12** (1.00 equiv.), PPh_3 (1.00 equiv.), *n*- Bu_4NOAc (3.00 equiv.) in DMF (26–28 mL/mmol) and stirred in a pre-heated oil bath for 16 h at 100 °C. Then the reaction mixture was allowed to reach r.t. and sat. aq. NH_4Cl solution and H_2O were added. The aqueous layer was extracted with MTBE, the combined organic extracts were washed with brine, dried over $MgSO_4$ and the solvent was removed *in vacuo*. The residue was purified by CC to give **8**.

1-Iodo-2-phenoxybenzene (5a) :

A solution of KI (9.63 g, 58.0 mmol, 2.00 equiv.) and $NaNO_2$ (4.66 g, 67.5 mmol, 2.00 equiv.) in water (25 mL) was added dropwise to a solution of 2-phenoxyaniline (5.00 g, 27.0 mmol, 1.00 equiv.) and *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (15.4 g, 81.0 mmol, 3.00 equiv.) in CH_3CN (300 mL) and stirred at r.t. for 45 min. Then the reaction mixture was treated with sat. aq. $NaHCO_3$ until pH 9–10 was reached and sat. aq. $Na_2S_2O_3$ (140 mL) was added. After extraction with $EtOAc$ (3 × 500 mL), the combined organic extracts were dried over $MgSO_4$ and the solvent was removed *in vacuo*. CC (SiO_2 , PE) yielded the desired product (7.21 g, 24.3 mmol, 90%) as a yellow oil. TLC R_f 0.34 (PE); IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3051, 1228; UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 270 nm (3.322), 277 (3.318); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) : 6.83–6.90 (2H, m, 3-H, 5-H), 6.94–6.98 (2H, m, 2'-H, 6'-H), 7.10 (1H, dt, J 7.4, 1.0 Hz, 4'-H), 7.24–7.35 (3H, m, 4-H, 3'-H, 5'-H), 7.85 (1H, dd, J 7.8, 1.6 Hz, 6-H); ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) : 88.9 (C-1), 118.4 (C-2', C-6'), 119.4 (C-3), 123.4 (C-4'), 125.3

(C-5), 129.6 (C-4), 129.8 (C-3', C-5'), 139.9 (C-6), 156.5 (C-1'), 156.8 (C-2); MS (EI) : m/z (%) : 296.0 (100) $[M]^+$, 169.1 (59) $[M-I]^+$, 141.1 (38) $[M-I-CO]^+$; $C_{12}H_9IO$ (296.10) calcd. : 295.9698 $[M]^+$, found : 295.9699 (EI HRMS).

4-Phenyl-1-(2-iodo-1-phenoxy)benzene (5b) :

A solution of KI (5.22 g, 31.4 mmol, 2.50 equiv.) and $NaNO_2$ (1.76 g, 25.2 mmol, 2.00 equiv.) in water (50 mL) was added dropwise to a solution of 4-phenyl-1-(2-aminophenoxy)benzene **14b** (3.28 g, 12.6 mmol, 1.00 equiv.) and *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (7.16 g, 37.7 mmol, 3.00 equiv.) in CH_3CN (300 mL) and stirred at r.t. for 2 h. Then the reaction mixture was treated with sat. aq. $NaHCO_3$ solution (300 mL) and extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3 × 300 mL). The combined organic extracts were concentrated *in vacuo*, diluted with CH_2Cl_2 (200 mL), washed with sat. aq. $Na_2S_2O_3$ (100 mL), dried over Na_2SO_4 and the solvent was removed *in vacuo*. CC (SiO_2 , *n*-pentane) yielded the desired product (3.56 g, 9.60 mmol, 76%) as a yellow solid. TLC R_f 0.38 (PE); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 201 nm (4.797), 260 (4.399); IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 1511, 1483, 1461, 1436, 1229, 1167, 1018, 835, 758, 695; 1H NMR (600 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) : 6.89 (1H, ddd, J 8.7, 7.6, 1.4 Hz, 4-H), 6.96 (1H, dd, J 8.1, 1.4 Hz, 6-H), 7.01–7.05 (2H, m, 3'-H, 5'-H), 7.27–7.35 (2H, m, 5-H, 4''-H), 7.40–7.44 (2H, m, 2''-H, 6''-H), 7.54–7.57 (4H, m, 2'-H, 6'-H, 3''-H, 5''-H), 7.87 (1H, dd, J 7.9, 1.4 Hz, 3-H); ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) : 89.0 (C-2), 118.5 (C-3', C-5'), 119.6 (C-6), 125.4 (C-4), 126.8 (C-3'', C-5''), 127.0 (C-4''), 128.4 (C-2', C-6'), 128.7 (C-2'', C-6''), 129.6 (C-5), 136.4 (C-1''), 139.8 (C-3), 140.4 (C-4'), 156.3 (C-1', C-1); MS (EI) m/z (%) : 372.0 (100) $[M+H]^+$.

4-tert-Butyl-1-(2-iodo-1-phenoxy)benzene (5c) :

A solution of KI (5.06 g, 30.5 mmol, 2.50 equiv.) and NaNO₂ (1.68 g, 24.4 mmol, 2.00 equiv.) in water (50 mL) was added dropwise to a solution of 4-*tert*-butyl-1-(2-aminophenoxy)benzene **14c** (2.95 g, 12.2 mmol, 1.00 equiv.) and *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (6.96 g, 36.6 mmol, 3.00 equiv.) in CH₃CN (300 mL) and stirred at r.t. for 2.5 h. Then the reaction mixture was treated with sat. aq. NaHCO₃ (200 mL) and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 300 mL). The combined organic extracts were concentrated *in vacuo*, diluted in CH₂Cl₂ (200 mL), washed with sat. aq. Na₂S₂O₃ (100 mL), dried over Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was removed *in vacuo*. CC (SiO₂, *n*-pentane) yielded the desired product (2.81 g, 7.99 mmol, 66%) as a colourless oil. TLC *R*_f 0.27 (PE/EtOAc 100/1); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm⁻¹): 1506, 1462, 1232, 1171, 1017, 830, 750, 544; UV (CH₃CN) $\lambda_{\max}$ (lg ϵ): 275 nm (3.432); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 1.31 (9H, s, C(CH₃)₃), 6.83 (1H, td, *J* 7.8, 1.4 Hz, 4-H), 6.86 (1H, dd, *J* 8.2, 1.4 Hz, 6-H), 6.88–6.93 (2H, m, 2'-H, 6'-H), 7.22–7.27 (1H, m, 5-H), 7.31–7.36 (2H, m, 3'-H, 5'-H), 7.83 (1H, dd, *J* 7.9, 1.4 Hz, 3-H); ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 31.5 (C(CH₃)₃), 34.4 (C(CH₃)₃), 88.5 (C-2), 118.0 (C-2', C-6'), 118.8 (C-6), 124.9 (C-4), 126.5 (C-3', C-5'), 129.4 (C-5), 139.7 (C-3), 146.3 (C-4'), 154.2 (C-1'), 156.8 (C-1); MS (EI) *m/z* (%): 337.0 (100) [M-CH₃]⁺, 352.0 (57) [M]⁺.

1-Bromo-2-(*prop*-2-yn-1-yloxy)benzene (**11a**):

A suspension of 2-bromophenol **9a** (500 mg, 2.89 mmol, 1.00 equiv.), propargyl bromide (80 m% in toluene, 311 μ L, 2.89 mmol, 1.00 equiv.) and K₂CO₃ (999 mg, 7.22 mmol, 2.50 equiv.) in CH₃CN (30 mL) was stirred for 16 h in a preheated oil bath at 60 °C. Then the reaction was allowed to reach r.t. and H₂O (40 mL) and EtOAc (30 mL) were added. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous phase was extracted with EtOAc (4 × 30 mL). The combined organic extracts were washed with brine (50 mL), dried over MgSO₄ and the solvent was removed *in vacuo* to obtain the desired product (610 mg, 2.89 mmol, quant.) as a yellow oil without further purification. TLC *R*_f 0.26 (PE/EtOAc 40/1); UV (CH₃CN)

$\lambda_{\max}$ (lg ϵ): 197 nm (4.658), 274 (3.360), 281 (3.315); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm⁻¹): 3291, 2123, 1475, 1228, 1052, 1031, 1017, 745; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 2.54 (1H, t, *J* 2.4 Hz, 3'-H), 4.78 (2H, d, *J* 2.4 Hz, 1'-H₂), 6.89 (1H, td, *J* 7.7, 1.4 Hz, 5-H), 7.07 (1H, dd, *J* 8.4, 1.4 Hz, 3-H), 7.28 (1H, ddd, *J* 8.4, 7.7, 1.6 Hz, 4-H), 7.56 (1H, dd, *J* 7.7, 1.6 Hz, 6-H); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 57.0 (C-1'), 76.3 (C-3'), 78.1 (C-2'), 112.6 (C-1), 114.4 (C-3), 123.0 (C-5), 128.5 (C-4), 133.7 (C-6), 154.2 (C-2); MS (EI, 70 eV) *m/z* (%): 210.0 (23) [M(⁷⁹Br)]⁺, 131.0 (100) [M-Br]⁺; C₉H₇BrO (211.06) calcd.: 209.9680, found: 209.9689 [M(⁷⁹Br)]⁺ (EI HRMS); calcd.: 211.9660, found: 211.9644 [M(⁸¹Br)]⁺ (EI HRMS).

2-Bromo-4-methyl-1-(*prop*-2-yn-1-yloxy)benzene (**11b**):

A suspension of 2-bromo-4-methylphenol **9b** (500 mg, 2.67 mmol, 1.00 equiv.), propargyl bromide (80 m% in toluene, 288 μ L, 2.67 mmol, 1.00 equiv.) and K₂CO₃ (1.11 g, 8.02 mmol, 3.00 equiv.) in CH₃CN (30 mL) was stirred for 16 h in a preheated oil bath at 60 °C. Then the reaction mixture was allowed to reach r.t. and H₂O (60 mL) and EtOAc (40 mL) were added. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous phase was extracted with EtOAc (3 × 40 mL). The combined organic layers were washed with brine (50 mL), dried over MgSO₄ and the solvent was removed *in vacuo*. The residue was purified via CC (SiO₂, PE/EtOAc 50/1) to obtain the desired product (598 mg, 2.66 mmol, 99%) as a colourless oil. TLC *R*_f 0.22 (PE/EtOAc 50/1); UV (CH₃CN) $\lambda_{\max}$ (lg ϵ): 200 nm (4.626), 280 (3.363); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm⁻¹): 3291, 1492, 1248, 1230, 1051, 1020, 1011, 802; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 2.29 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.52 (1H, t, *J* 2.4 Hz, 3'-H), 4.74 (2H, d, *J* 2.4 Hz, 1'-H₂), 6.96 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, 6-H), 7.07 (1H, ddd, *J* 8.3, 2.1, 0.7 Hz, 5-H), 7.38 (1H, dd, *J* 2.1, 0.6 Hz, 3-H); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 20.5 (CH₃), 57.3 (C-1'), 76.1 (C-3'), 78.4 (C-2'), 112.4 (C-2), 114.5 (C-6), 128.8 (C-5), 132.8 (C-4), 134.0 (C-3), 151.9 (C-1); MS (EI, 70 eV) *m/z* (%): 224.0 (36) [M(⁷⁹Br)]⁺, 145.1 (100) [M-Br]⁺; C₁₀H₉BrO (225.08) calcd.: 223.9837, found: 223.9834 [M(⁷⁹Br)]⁺ (EI HRMS).

2-Bromo-4-methoxy-1-(prop-2-yn-1-yloxy)benzene (11c) :

A suspension of 2-bromo-4-methoxyphenol **9c** (500 mg, 2.46 mmol, 1.00 equiv.) and K_2CO_3 (730 mg, 7.38 mmol, 3.00 equiv.) in DMF (30 mL) was warmed to 60 °C and stirred at this temperature for 30 min. The reaction mixture was cooled to 0 °C and a solution of propargyl bromide (80 m% in toluene, 270 μ L, 2.46 mmol, 1.00 equiv.) in DMF (15 mL) was added. The resulting mixture was warmed to r.t. and stirred at this temperature for 15 h. The reaction was finished by the addition of sat. aq. NH_4Cl solution (100 mL), the phases were separated and the aqueous phase was extracted with EtOAc (3 $\times$ 100 mL). The combined organic extracts were washed with H_2O (20 mL) and brine (3 $\times$ 20 mL), dried over $MgSO_4$ and the solvent was removed *in vacuo*. CC (SiO_2 , PE/MTBE 50/1) yielded the desired product (459 mg, 1.90 mmol, 77%) as a white solid. TLC R_f 0.15 (PE/MTBE 50/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 292 nm (3.520), 198 (4.521); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3288, 1601, 1575, 1486, 1274, 1205, 1035, 861; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) : 2.46–2.54 (1H, m, 3'-H), 3.74 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.68 (2H, d, J 2.4 Hz, 1'- H_2), 6.80 (1H, dd, J 9.0, 3.0 Hz, 5-H), 7.01 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz, 6-H), 7.10 (1H, d, J 3.0 Hz, 3-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) : 55.8 (OCH_3), 57.9 (C-1), 75.8 (C-3'), 78.4 (C-2'), 113.3 (C-2), 113.5 (C-6), 116.4 (C-5), 118.8 (C-3), 148.2 (C-1), 154.9 (C-4); MS (EI, 70 eV) m/z (%) : 201.0 (100) [$M-C_3H_3$], 240.0 (19) [M^+]. $C_{10}H_9BrO_2$ (240.00) calcd. : 239.9786, found : 239.9786 [M^+] (EI HRMS).

2-Bromo-4-fluoro-1-(prop-2-yn-1-yloxy)benzene (11d) :

A suspension of 2-bromo-4-fluorophenol **9d** (500 mg, 2.62 mmol, 1.00 equiv.), propargyl bromide (80 m% in toluene, 282 μ L, 2.62 mmol, 1.00 equiv.) and K_2CO_3 (1.09 g, 7.85 mmol, 3.00 equiv.) in CH_3CN (30 mL) was stirred in a preheated oil bath for 16 h at 60 °C.

Then the reaction mixture was allowed to reach r.t. and H_2O (30 mL) and EtOAc (30 mL) were added. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous phase was extracted with EtOAc (3 $\times$ 30 mL). The combined organic layers were washed with brine (50 mL), dried over $MgSO_4$ and the solvent was removed *in vacuo* to obtain the desired product (563 mg, 2.46 mmol, 94%) as a yellow solid without further purification. TLC R_f 0.13 (PE/EtOAc 40/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 281 nm (3.526); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3296, 2360, 2340, 1482, 1265, 1185, 1042, 786; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) : 2.54 (1H, t, J 2.4 Hz, 3'-H), 4.74 (2H, d, J 2.4 Hz, 1'- H_2), 6.96–7.07 (2H, m, 5-H, 6-H), 7.31 (1H, ddd, J 7.7, 2.7, 0.3 Hz, 3-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) : 57.8 (C-1'), 76.5 (C-3'), 78.0 (C-2'), 113.1 (d, J 10 Hz, C-2), 114.8 (d, J 23 Hz, C-5), 115.6 (d, J 9 Hz, C-6), 120.8 (d, J 26 Hz, C-3), 150.8, (d, J 3 Hz, C-1), 157.5 (d, J 244 Hz, C-4); MS (EI, 70 eV) m/z (%) : 230.0 (14) [$M(^{81}Br)^+$], 149 (47) [$M-Br$] $^+$. C_9H_8BrFO (229.05) calcd. : 227.9586, found : 227.9590 [$M(^{79}Br)^+$] (EI HRMS); calcd. : 229.9566, found : 229.9568 [$M(^{81}Br)^+$] (EI HRMS).

2-Bromo-1-((3-(2-phenoxyphenyl)prop-2-yn-1-yl)oxy)benzene (3a) :

A mixture of alkyne **11a** (128 mg, 608 μ mol, 1.20 equiv.), **5a** (150 mg, 507 μ mol, 1.00 equiv.), $Pd(PPh_3)_4$ (29.3 mg, 25.3 μ mol, 0.05 equiv.), CuI (9.65 mg, 50.6 μ mol, 0.10 equiv.) and $n-Bu_4NOAc$ (382 mg, 1.27 mmol, 2.50 equiv.) in 1,4-dioxane (5 mL) was treated according to GP1 for 1 h. CC (SiO_2 , PE/EtOAc 60/1) yielded the desired product (201 mg, 530 μ mol, quant.) as a yellow oil. TLC R_f 0.13 (PE/EtOAc 60/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 275 nm (3.651), 281 (3.665); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3062, 1475, 1444, 1255, 1224, 746, 690, 659; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) : 4.94 (2H, s, 1'- H_2), 6.83 (1H, ddd, J 7.9, 7.2, 1.6 Hz, 5-H), 6.90 (1H, dd, J 8.3, 1.0 Hz, 3''-H), 6.94–6.99 (2H, m, 2'''-H, 6'''-

H), 7.03–7.10 (2H, m, 3-H, 5''-H), 7.09–7.17 (2H, m, 4-H, 4'''-H), 7.24–7.29 (1H, m, 4''-H), 7.29–7.37 (2H, m, 3'''-H, 5'''-H), 7.47 (1H, dd, J 7.7, 1.7 Hz, 6''-H), 7.52 (1H, dd, J 7.9, 1.6 Hz, 6-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 57.8 (C-1'), 83.7 (C-3'), 88.3 (C-2'), 112.5 (C-1), 114.7 (C-3), 114.8 (C-1''), 118.6 (C-2''', C-6'''), 119.1 (C-3''), 122.7 (C-5), 123.4 (C-4'''), 123.4 (C-5''), 128.4 (C-4), 129.8 (C-3''', C-5'''), 130.3 (C-4''), 133.5 (C-6), 134.0 (C-6''), 154.3 (C-2), 157.3 (C-1'''), 158.0 (C-2''). MS (ESI, MeOH) m/z (%) : 379.0 (14) $[\text{M}^{(79)\text{Br}}+\text{H}]^+$, 398.1 (77) $[\text{M}^{(81)\text{Br}}+\text{NH}_4]^+$, 401.0 (100) $[\text{M}^{(79)\text{Br}}+\text{Na}]^+$. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{15}\text{BrO}_2$ (379.25) calcd. : 401.0148, found : 401.0147 $[\text{M}^{(79)\text{Br}}+\text{Na}]^+$ (ESI HRMS); calcd. : 403.0128, found. : 403.0126 $[\text{M}^{(81)\text{Br}}+\text{Na}]^+$ (ESI HRMS).

2-Bromo-4-methyl-1-((3-(2-phenoxyphenyl)prop-2-yn-1-yl)oxy)benzene (3b) :

A mixture of alkyne **11b** (137 mg, 608 μmol , 1.20 equiv.), **5a** (150 mg, 507 μmol , 1.00 equiv.), $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (29.3 mg, 25.3 μmol , 0.05 equiv.), CuI (9.65 mg, 50.6 μmol , 0.10 equiv.) and $n\text{-Bu}_4\text{NOAc}$ (382 mg, 1.27 mmol, 2.50 equiv.) in 1,4-dioxane (5 mL) was treated according to GP1 for 30 min. CC (SiO_2 , $n\text{-hexane}/\text{EtOAc}$ 60/1) yielded the desired product (198 mg, 503 μmol , 99%) as a yellow oil. TLC R_f 0.10 ($n\text{-hexane}/\text{EtOAc}$ 60/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 199 nm (4.862), 281 (3.694), 288 (3.710); IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 1482, 1443, 1253, 1223, 1048, 798, 750, 689; ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 2.24 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.89 (2H, s, 1'- H_2), 6.88–6.91 (2H, m, 6-H, 3''-H), 6.94–6.98 (3H, m, 5-H, 2'''-H, 6'''-H), 7.06 (1H, td, J 7.6, 1.1 Hz, 5''-H), 7.11 (1H, tt, J 7.7, 1.0 Hz, 4'''-H), 7.27 (1H, ddd, J 8.4, 7.6, 1.7 Hz, 4''-H), 7.31–7.34 (3H, m, 3-H, 3'''-H, 5'''-H), 7.46 (1H, dd, J 7.6, 1.7 Hz, 6''-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 20.4 (CH_3), 58.2 (C-1'), 83.6 (C-3'), 88.5 (C-2'), 112.2 (C-2), 114.8 (C-1''), 114.9 (C-5), 118.6 (C-2''', C-6'''), 119.0 (C-3''), 123.4 (C-4'''), 123.4 (C-

5''), 128.8 (C-6), 129.7 (C-3''', C-5'''), 130.2 (C-4''), 132.4 (C-4), 133.8 (C-3), 134.0 (C-6''), 152.1 (C-1), 157.2 (C-1'''), 157.9 (C-2''). MS (ESI, MeOH) m/z (%) : 393.0 (13) $[\text{M}^{(79)\text{Br}}+\text{H}]^+$, 412.1 (100) $[\text{M}^{(81)\text{Br}}+\text{NH}_4]^+$, 417.0 (82) $[\text{M}^{(81)\text{Br}}+\text{Na}]^+$. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{BrO}_2$ (393.28) calcd. : 393.0485, found : 393.0477 $[\text{M}^{(79)\text{Br}}+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS); calcd. : 395.0465, found : 395.0464 $[\text{M}^{(81)\text{Br}}+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS).

2-Bromo-4-methoxy-1-((3-(2-phenoxyphenyl)prop-2-yn-1-yl)oxy)benzene (3c) :

A mixture of alkyne **11c** (49.0 mg, 203 μmol , 1.20 equiv.), **5a** (50.0 mg, 169 μmol , 1.00 equiv.), $\text{PdCl}_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ (5.9 mg, 8.45 μmol , 0.05 equiv.), CuI (1.1 mg, 16.9 μmol , 0.10 equiv.) and $n\text{-Bu}_4\text{NOAc}$ (127 mg, 423 μmol , 2.50 equiv.) in 1,4-dioxane (5 mL) was treated according to GP1 for 1 h. CC (SiO_2 , PE/MTBE 10/1) yielded the desired product (69.8 mg, quant.) as a yellow oil. TLC R_f 0.15 (PE/MTBE 50/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 291 nm (3.805); IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 1589, 1572, 1482, 1440, 1253, 1205, 1036, 863, 796, 750; ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 3.70 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.84 (2H, s, 1'- H_2), 6.62 (1H, dd, J 9.0, 3.0 Hz, 6-H), 6.87 (1H, dd, J 8.3, 1.1 Hz, 3''-H), 6.95 (2H, dt, J 7.7, 1.1 Hz, 2'''-H, 6'''-H), 7.00 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz, 5-H), 7.04 (1H, td, J 7.6, 1.1 Hz, 4'''-H), 7.06 (1H, d, J 3.0 Hz, 3-H), 7.09 (1H, tt, J 7.5, 1.1 Hz, 5''-H), 7.22–7.27 (1H, m, 4''-H), 7.29–7.33 (2H, m, 3'''-H, 5'''-H), 7.45 (1H, dd, J 7.7, 1.7 Hz, 6''-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 55.8 (OCH_3), 58.9 (C-1'), 83.4 (C-3'), 88.5 (C-2'), 113.3 (C-2), 113.5 (C-6), 114.7 (C-1''), 116.8 (C-5), 118.5 (C-2''', C-6'''), 118.6 (C-3), 118.8 (C-3''), 123.2 (C-5'', C-4'''), 129.6 (C-3''', C-5'''), 130.0 (C-4''), 133.7 (C-6''), 148.4 (C-1), 154.7 (C-4), 157.0 (C-1'''), 157.7 (C-2''). MS (ESI, MeOH) m/z (%) : 431.0 (100) $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$, 447.0 (26) $[\text{M}+\text{K}]^+$, 841.1 (65) $[2\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{BrO}_3$ (409.27) calcd. : 409.0434, found : 409.0422 $[\text{M}^{(79)\text{Br}}+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS); calcd. :

411.0414, found : 411.0396 [M(⁸¹Br)+H]⁺ (ESI HRMS); calcd. : 431.0253; found : 431.0240 [M(⁸¹Br)+H]⁺ (ESI HRMS); calcd. : 433.0234, found : 433.0223 [M(⁸¹Br)+Na]⁺ (ESI HRMS).

2-Bromo-4-fluoro-1-((3-(2-phenoxyphenyl)prop-2-yn-1-yl)oxy)benzene (**3d**) :

A mixture of alkyne **11d** (150 mg, 655 μmol, 1.20 equiv.), **5a** (162 mg, 546 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), PdCl₂(PPh₃)₂ (19.2 mg, 27.3 μmol, 0.05 equiv.), CuI (10.4 mg, 54.6 μmol, 0.10 equiv.) and *n*-Bu₄NOAc (411 mg, 1.36 mmol, 2.50 equiv.) in 1,4-dioxane (5 mL) was treated according to GP1 for 1.5 h. CC (SiO₂, PE/EtOAc 60/1) yielded the desired product (216 mg, 544 μmol, quant.) as a yellow oil. TLC *R*_f 0.14 (PE/EtOAc 50/1); UV (CH₃CN) λ_{max} (lg ε) : 289 nm (3.704); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm⁻¹) : 1480, 1253, 1223, 1184, 1039, 797, 750, 732; ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 4.90 (2H, s, 1'-H₂), 6.79 (1H, ddd, *J* 9.0, 7.9, 3.0 Hz, 5-H), 6.90 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, 3''-H), 6.93–6.96 (2H, m, 2'''-H, 6'''-H), 7.00 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0, 4.8 Hz, 6-H), 7.07 (1H, td, *J* 7.7, 1.0 Hz, 5''-H), 7.11 (1H, m_c, 4'''-H), 7.25 (1H, dd, *J* 7.8, 3.0 Hz, 3-H), 7.27–7.30 (1H, m, 4''-H), 7.31–7.35 (2H, m, 3'''-H, 5'''-H), 7.46 (1H, dd, *J* 7.7, 1.6 Hz, 6''-H); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 58.6 (C-1'), 84.0 (C-3'), 88.0 (C-2'), 112.9 (d, *J* 11 Hz, C-2), 114.7 (d, *J* 23 Hz, C-5), 114.7 (C-1''), 115.9 (d, *J* 9 Hz, C-6), 118.6 (C-2'''), C-6'''), 119.2 (C-3''), 120.5 (d, *J* 26 Hz, C-3), 123.5 (C-4'''), 123.5 (C-5''), 129.9 (C-3''', C-5'''), 130.4 (C-4''), 133.9 (C-6''), 150.9 (d, *J* 4 Hz, C-1), 157.3 (d, *J* 244 Hz, C-4), 157.3 (C-1'''), 158.0 (C-2''). MS (ESI, MeOH) *m/z* (%) : 414.0 (81) [M(⁷⁹Br)+NH₄]⁺, 416.0 (77) [M(⁸¹Br)+NH₄]⁺, 419.0 (100) [M(⁷⁹Br)+Na]⁺, 421.0 (94) [M(⁸¹Br)+Na]⁺. C₂₁H₁₄BrFO₂ (397.24) calcd. : 419.0053, found : 419.0052 [M(⁷⁹Br)+Na]⁺ (ESI HRMS), calcd. : 421.0034, found : 421.0031 [M(⁸¹Br)+Na]⁺ (ESI HRMS).

9-(Benzofuran-3-yl)-9H-xanthen (**7a**) :

A mixture of alkyne **3a** (50.0 mg, 132 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), PPh₃ (34.6 mg, 132 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), K₂CO₃ (91.1 mg, 659 μmol, 5.00 equiv.) and Pd(OAc)₂ (5.92 mg, 26.4 μmol, 0.20 equiv.) in DMF (2.5 mL) was treated according to GP2 for 4 h. Work up : sat. aq. NH₄Cl solution (5 mL), H₂O (5 mL), MTBE (3 × 8 mL). CC (SiO₂, *n*-hexane/CH₂Cl₂ 30/1) yielded the desired product (15.9 mg, 53.3 μmol, 40%) as a white solid. TLC *R*_f 0.19 (*n*-hexane/CH₂Cl₂ 15/1); UV (CH₃CN) λ_{max} (lg ε) : 247 nm (4.148), 275 (3.616), 282 (3.635); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm⁻¹) : 1602, 1575, 1478, 1449, 1253, 1097, 857, 745; ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 5.50 (1H, s, 9-H), 6.96 (2H, td, *J* 7.7, 1.1 Hz, 2-H, 7-H), 7.03 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, 5'-H), 7.13 (2H, d, *J* 7.7 Hz, 1-H, 8-H), 7.15–7.19 (3H, m, 4-H, 5-H, 4'-H), 7.19–7.25 (3H, m, 3-H, 6-H, 6'-H), 7.44 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, 7'-H), 7.66 (1H, s, 2'-H); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 34.2 (C-9), 111.7 (C-7'), 116.7 (C-4, C-5), 120.7 (C-4'), 122.4 (C-1a, C-8a), 122.7 (C-5'), 123.4 (C-2, C-7), 124.0 (C-3'), 124.5 (C-6'), 126.1 (C-3a'), 128.4 (C-3, C-6), 129.4 (C-1, C-8), 142.0 (C-2'), 151.5 (C-4a, C-5a), 156.2 (C-7a'); MS (EI, 70 eV) *m/z* (%) : 297.1 (96) [M-H]⁺, 298.1 (100) [M]⁺. C₂₁H₁₄O₂ (298.34) calcd. : 321.0886, found : 321.0885 [M+Na]⁺ (ESI HRMS).

9-(5-Methylbenzofuran-3-yl)-9H-xanthen (**7b**) :

A mixture of alkyne **3b** (51.7 mg, 131 μmol, 1.00

equiv.), PPh_3 (34.5 mg, 131 μmol , 1.00 equiv.), K_2CO_3 (90.8 mg, 657 μmol , 5.00 equiv.) and $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$ (5.90 mg, 26.3 μmol , 0.20 equiv.) in DMF (2.5 mL) was treated according to GP2 for 3 h. Work up : sat. aq. NH_4Cl solution (5 mL), H_2O (5 mL), MTBE (4×8 mL). CC (SiO_2 , *n*-hexane $\rightarrow$ *n*-hexane/ CH_2Cl_2 20/1) yielded the desired product (26.5 mg, 84.8 μmol , 65%) as a yellow solid. TLC R_f 0.16 (*n*-hexane/ CH_2Cl_2 15/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 196 nm (4.746), 201 (4.741), 250 (4.164), 282 (3.698), 289 (3.698); IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 2921, 1574, 1476, 1446, 1251, 1094, 747, 689; ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 2.27 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.47 (1H, s, 9-H), 6.94 (1H, d, J 1.0 Hz, 4'-H), 6.96 (2H, td, J 7.5, 1.1 Hz, 2-H, 7-H), 7.02 (1H, dd, J 8.4, 1.0 Hz, 6'-H), 7.10–7.13 (2H, m, 1-H, 8-H), 7.17 (2H, dd, J 8.2, 1.1 Hz, 4-H, 5-H), 7.21–7.25 (2H, m, 3-H, 6-H), 7.32 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz, 7'-H), 7.60 (1H, s, 2'-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 21.6 (CH_3), 34.2 (C-9), 111.1 (C-7'), 116.6 (C-4, C-5), 120.4 (C-4'), 122.5 (C-1a, C-8a), 123.3 (C-2, C-7), 123.4 (C-3'), 125.7 (C-6'), 126.1 (C-3a'), 128.2 (C-3, C-6), 129.3 (C-1, C-8), 132.0 (C-5'), 142.4 (C-2'), 151.4 (C-4a, C-5a), 154.5 (C-7a'); MS (EI, 70 eV) m/z (%) : 311.1 (91) $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^+$, 312.1 (100) $[\text{M}]^+$. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ (312.37) calcd. : 311.1072, found : 311.1078 $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^+$ (EI HRMS); calcd. : 312.1150, found : 312.1149 $[\text{M}]^+$ (EI HRMS).

9-(5-Methoxybenzofuran-3-yl)-9H-xanthen (7c) :

A mixture of alkyne **3c** (20.0 mg, 48.9 μmol , 1.00 equiv.), PPh_3 (12.7 mg, 48.9 μmol , 1.00 equiv.), K_2CO_3 (33.0 mg, 244 μmol , 5.00 equiv.) and $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$ (2.5 mg, 9.78 μmol , 0.20 equiv.) in DMF (1.8 mL) was treated according to GP2 for 2 h. Work up : sat. aq. NH_4Cl solution (5 mL), H_2O (5 mL), MTBE (3×7 mL). CC (SiO_2 , PE/MTBE 50/1) yielded the desired product (10.7 mg, 32.6 μmol , 67%) as a yellow oil. TLC R_f = 0.22 (PE/MTBE 50/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 205 nm

(4.698), 239 (4.169), 293 (3.858); IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 1599, 1474, 1447, 1317, 1253, 1101, 1025, 926, 794, 750; ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 3.62 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.45 (1H, s, 9-H), 6.60 (1H, d, J 2.6 Hz, 6'-H), 6.79 (1H, dd, J 8.9, 2.6 Hz, 4'-H), 6.96 (2H, td, J 7.5, 1.3 Hz, 2-H, 7-H), 7.13 (2H, dt, J 7.7, 1.2 Hz, 1-H, 8-H), 7.15 (2H, dd, J 8.2, 1.3 Hz, 4-H, 5-H), 7.19–7.23 (2H, m, 3-H, 6-H), 7.31 (1H, d, J 8.9 Hz, 3'-H), 7.62 (1H, s, 2'-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 34.1 (C-9), 55.7 (OCH_3), 103.1 (C-6'), 111.8 (C-3'), 112.7 (C-4'), 116.4 (C-4, C-5), 122.1 (C-1a, C-8a), 123.2 (C-2, C-7), 123.9 (C-1'), 126.5 (C-6a'), 128.1 (C-3, C-6), 129.2 (C-1, C-8), 142.4 (C-2'), 150.8 (C-3a'), 151.2 (C-4a, C-5a), 155.4 (C-5'); MS (EI, 70 eV) m/z (%) : 327.1 (59) $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^+$, 351.1 (100) $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$, 367.1 (34) $[\text{M}+\text{K}]^+$. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ (320.09) calcd. : 351.0992, found : 351.0981 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ (ESI HRMS).

9-(5-Fluorobenzofuran-3-yl)-9H-xanthen (7d) :

A mixture of alkyne **3d** (52.0 mg, 131 μmol , 1.00 equiv.), PPh_3 (34.3 mg, 131 μmol , 1.00 equiv.), K_2CO_3 (90.5 mg, 655 μmol , 5.00 equiv.) and $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$ (5.88 mg, 26.2 μmol , 0.20 equiv.) in DMF (2.5 mL) was treated according to GP2 for 2 h. Work up : sat. aq. NH_4Cl solution (5 mL), H_2O (5 mL), MTBE (3×7 mL). CC (SiO_2 , *n*-hexane/ CH_2Cl_2 30/1) yielded the desired product (22.7 mg, 71.8 μmol , 55%) as a white solid. TLC R_f 0.30 (PE/EtOAc 30/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 248 nm (4.125), 280 (3.746), 287 (3.728); IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 2924, 1478, 1471, 1448, 1252, 1163, 1098, 751; ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 5.46 (1H, s, 9-H), 6.80 (1H, dd, J 8.7, 2.6 Hz, 4'-H), 6.91 (1H, td, J 8.9, 2.6 Hz, 6'-H), 6.98 (2H, td, J 7.7, 1.1 Hz, 2-H, 7-H), 7.11 (2H, d, J 7.7 Hz, 1-H, 8-H), 7.17 (2H, dd, J 8.2, 1.1 Hz, 4-H, 5-H), 7.22–7.26 (2H, m, 3-H, 6-H), 7.35 (1H, dd, J 8.9, 4.1 Hz, 7'-H), 7.69 (1H, s, 2'-H);

^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 34.2 (C-9), 106.3 (d, J 26 Hz, C-4'), 112.3 (d, J 13 Hz, C-7'), 112.4 (d, J 24 Hz, C-6'), 116.9 (C-4, C-5), 121.9 (C-1a, C-8a), 123.5 (C-2, C-7), 124.3 (d, J 5 Hz, C-3'), 126.9 (d, J 11 Hz, C-3a'), 128.6 (C-3, C-6), 129.3 (C-1, C-8), 143.6 (C-2'), 151.5 (C-4a, C-5a), 152.4 (C-7a'), 159.0 (d, J 238 Hz, C-5'); MS (EI, 70 eV) m/z (%) : 315.1 (87) $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^+$, 316.1 (100) $[\text{M}]^+$. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{13}\text{FO}_2$ (316.33) calcd. : 339.0792, found : 339.0790 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ (ESI HRMS).

N-(2-Bromophenyl)-*N*-(prop-2-yn-1-yl)acetamide (**12a**) :

A solution of amide **10a** (50 mg, 2.33 mmol, 1.00 equiv.), propargyl bromide (80 m% in toluene, 230 μL , 2.57 mmol, 1.10 equiv.), KOH (147 mg, 2.57 mmol, 1.10 equiv.) and BnEt_3NCl (108 mg, 467 μmol , 0.20 equiv.) in THF (24 mL) was stirred for 3 h at r.t. The reaction was finished by the addition of sat. aq. NH_4Cl solution (30 mL) and the aqueous phase was extracted with EtOAc (3 $\times$ 50 mL). The combined organic extracts were dried over Na_2SO_4 and the solvent was removed *in vacuo* to obtain the desired product (612 mg, 96%) as a brown oil. TLC R_f 0.48 (PE/MTBE 1/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 266 nm (2.577), 195 (4.572); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 1664, 1474, 1381, 1285, 1224, 1016, 742; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 1.80 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.16 (1H, t, J 2.5 Hz, 3'-H), 3.82 (1H, dd, J 17.4, 2.5 Hz, 1'- H_a), 5.07 (1H, dd, J 17.4, 2.5 Hz, 1'- H_b), 7.24–7.27 (1H, m, 6-H), 7.38–7.43 (2H, m, 4-H, 5-H), 7.66–7.70 (1H, m, 3-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 22.2 (COCH_3), 36.7 (C-1'), 72.4 (C-3'), 78.6 (C-2'), 123.6 (C-2), 128.6 (C-4), 130.2 (C-6), 131.2 (C-5), 133.7 (C-3), 140.3 (C-1), 169.7 (CO); MS (ESI, MeOH) m/z (%) : 276.0 (99) $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$, 527.0 (100) $[\text{2M}+\text{Na}]^+$. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{BrNO}$ (252.10) calcd. : 252.0019, found : 252.0020 $[\text{M}^{(79)\text{Br}}+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS); calcd. : 253.9998, found : 253.9999 $[\text{M}^{(81)\text{Br}}+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS); calcd. : 273.9838, found : 273.9835 $[\text{M}^{(79)\text{Br}}+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS).

N-(2-Bromo-4-methylphenyl)-*N*-(prop-2-yn-1-yl)acetamide (**12b**) :

A solution of amide **10b** (500 mg, 2.19 mmol, 1.00 equiv.), propargyl bromide (80 m% in toluene, 260 μL , 2.41 mmol, 1.10 equiv.), KOH (123 mg, 2.41 mmol, 1.10 equiv.) and BnEt_3NCl (99.9 mg, 438 μmol , 0.20 equiv.) in THF (20 mL) was stirred for 40 h at r.t. The reaction was finished by the addition of sat. aq. NH_4Cl solution (20 mL) and H_2O (10 mL) and the aqueous phase was extracted with EtOAc (3 $\times$ 20 mL). The combined organic extracts were washed with brine (30 mL), dried over MgSO_4 and the solvent was removed *in vacuo*. CC (SiO_2 , PE/EtOAc 4/1) yielded the desired product (562 mg, 2.11 mmol, 96%) as a yellow oil. TLC R_f 0.24 (PE/EtOAc 4/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 199 nm (4.623); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 3295, 1665, 1492, 1380, 1286, 1228, 737, 576; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 1.82 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.17 (1H, t, J 2.5 Hz, 3'-H), 2.38 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.82 (1H, dd, J 17.4, 2.5 Hz, 1'- H_a), 5.07 (1H, dd, J 17.4, 2.5 Hz, 1'- H_b), 7.19 (1H, ddd, J 8.0, 1.8, 0.7 Hz, 5-H), 7.30 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, 6-H), 7.51 (1H, dd, J 1.8, 0.7 Hz, 3-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 21.2 (CH_3), 22.4 (COCH_3), 36.9 (C-1'), 72.5 (C-3'), 78.9 (C-2'), 123.3 (C-2), 129.5 (C-5), 130.9 (C-6), 134.2 (C-3), 137.8 (C-4), 140.8 (C-1), 170.1 (CO); MS (ESI, MeOH) m/z (%) : 266.0 (40) $[\text{M}^{(79)\text{Br}}+\text{H}]^+$, 555.0 (100) $[\text{2M}+\text{Na}]^+$. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrNO}$ (266.13) calcd. : 266.0175, found : 266.0182 $[\text{M}^{(79)\text{Br}}+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS); calcd. : 268.0155, found : 268.0162 $[\text{M}^{(81)\text{Br}}+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS).

N-(2-Bromo-4-fluorophenyl)-*N*-(prop-2-yn-1-yl)acetamide (**12c**) :

A solution of amide **10c** (500 mg, 2.15 mmol, 1.00 equiv.), propargyl bromide (80 m% in toluene, 255 μL , 2.37 mmol, 1.10 equiv.), KOH (121 mg, 2.37 mmol, 1.10 equiv.) and BnEt_3NCl (98.2 mg, 431 μmol , 0.20 equiv.) in THF (20 mL) was stirred for 20 h at r.t. The reaction was finished by the addition of sat. aq. NH_4Cl solution (20 mL) and H_2O (10 mL) and the aqueous layer was extracted with EtOAc (3 $\times$ 20 mL). The combined organic extracts were washed with brine (30 mL), dried over MgSO_4 and the solvent was removed *in vacuo*. CC (SiO_2 , PE/EtOAc 5/1) yielded the desired product (512 mg, 1.90 mmol, 88%) as yellow solid. TLC R_f 0.18 (PE/EtOAc 5/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ): 269 nm (2.838); IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}): 3300, 1667, 1487, 1382, 1286, 1258, 1193, 860; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 1.82 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.19 (1H, t, J 2.5 Hz, 3'-H), 3.82 (1H, dd, J 17.4, 2.5 Hz, 1'- H_a), 5.09 (1H, dd, J 17.4, 2.5 Hz, 1'- H_b), 7.13 (1H, ddd, J 8.7, 7.6, 2.9 Hz, 5-H), 7.40–7.47 (2H, m, 3-H, 6-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 22.4 (COCH_3), 36.9 (C-1'), 72.9 (C-3'), 78.6 (C-2'), 115.9 (d, J 22 Hz, C-5), 121.1 (d, J 26 Hz, C-3), 124.5 (d, J 11 Hz, C-2), 132.4 (d, J 9 Hz, C-6), 136.8 (d, J 4 Hz, C-1), 162.0 (d, J 254 Hz, C-4), 169.9 (CO); MS (ESI, MeOH) m/z (%): 270.0 (100) $[\text{M}(^{79}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$, 563.0 (61) $[\text{2M}+\text{H}]^+$. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{BrFNO}$ (270.10) calcd.: 269.9924, found: 269.9930 $[\text{M}(^{79}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS); calcd.: 271.9904, found: 271.9906 $[\text{M}(^{81}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS).

N-(2-Bromophenyl)-*N*-(3-(2-phenoxyphenyl)prop-2-yn-1-yl)acetamide (**4a**):

A mixture of alkyne **12a** (100 mg, 397 μmol , 1.00 equiv.), **5a** (141 mg, 476 μmol , 1.20 equiv.), $\text{PdCl}_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ (13.8 mg, 19.8 μmol , 0.05 equiv.), CuI (2.6 mg, 39.7 μmol , 0.10 equiv.) and *n*- Bu_4NOAc (297 mg, 991 μmol , 2.50 equiv.) in 1,4-dioxane (7 mL) was treated according to GP1 for 50 min. CC (SiO_2 , PE/MTBE 6/1) yielded the desired product (125 mg, 297 μmol , 75%) as a brown

oil. TLC R_f 0.52 (PE/MTBE 1/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ): 252 nm (4.196), 270 (3.371), 279 (3.380), 289 (3.443), 298 (3.363); IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}): 1669, 1587, 1475, 1442, 1381, 1253, 1223, 869, 753; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 1.76 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.97 (1H, d, J 17.6 Hz, 1'- H_a), 5.30 (1H, d, J 17.6 Hz, 1'- H_b), 6.83 (1H, dd, J 8.3, 1.1 Hz, 3''-H), 6.91–6.95 (2H, m, 2''-H, 6'''-H), 7.01 (1H, td, J 7.6, 1.1 Hz, 5''-H), 7.08 (2H, qd, J 8.0, 1.3 Hz, 4'''-H, 5-H) 7.15 (1H, td, J 7.8, 1.7 Hz, 4-H), 7.21 (1H, ddd, J 8.2, 7.4, 1.7 Hz, 4''-H), 7.28–7.34 (3H, m, 3'''-H, 5'''-H, 6-H), 7.36 (1H, dd, J 7.7, 1.7 Hz, 6''-H), 7.60 (1H, dd, J 8.0, 1.5 Hz, 3-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 22.3 (COCH_3), 37.4 (C-1'), 80.0 (C-3'), 88.8 (C-2'), 115.2 (C-1''), 118.5 (C-2''), 118.7 (C-3''), 123.2 (C-5'', C-4'''), 123.6 (C-2), 128.4 (C-5), 129.5 (C-4''), 129.6 (C-3''', C-5'''), 129.9 (C-4), 131.5 (C-6), 133.4 (C-3), 133.6 (C-6''), 140.2 (C-1), 157.1 (C-1'''), 157.5 (C-2''), 169.6 (CO); MS (ESI, MeOH) m/z (%): 444.1 (34) $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$, 863.1 (100) $[\text{2M}+\text{Na}]^+$. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{18}\text{BrNO}_2$ (420.29) calcd.: 420.0594, found: 420.0581 $[\text{M}(^{79}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS); calcd.: 422.0574, found: 422.0558 $[\text{M}(^{81}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS); calcd.: 442.0413, found: 442.0404 $[\text{M}(^{79}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS); calcd.: 444.0394, found: 444.0386 $[\text{M}(^{81}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS).

N-(2-Bromo-4-methylphenyl)-*N*-(3-(2-phenoxyphenyl)prop-2-yn-1-yl)acetamide (**4b**):

A mixture of alkyne **12b** (97.1 mg, 365 μmol , 1.20 equiv.), **5a** (90.0 mg, 304 μmol , 1.00 equiv.), $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (17.6 mg, 15.2 μmol , 0.05 equiv.), CuI (5.79 mg, 30.4 μmol , 0.10 equiv.) and *n*- Bu_4NOAc (229 mg, 760 μmol , 2.50 equiv.) in 1,4-dioxane (3 mL) was treated according to GP1 for 1 h. CC (SiO_2 , PE/EtOAc 6/1 $\rightarrow$ 4/1) yielded the desired product (129 mg, 297 μmol , 98%) as a yellow oil. TLC R_f 0.21 (PE/EtOAc 4/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ): 252 nm (4.206), 289 (3.481); IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}): 1667, 1483, 1380, 1254, 1223, 869, 752, 690;

^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 1.78 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.29 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.97 (1H, d, J 17.5 Hz, $1'\text{-H}_a$), 5.31 (1H, d, J 17.5 Hz, $1'\text{-H}_b$), 6.83–6.87 (2H, m, 5-H, $3''\text{-H}$), 6.94–6.98 (2H, m, $2'''\text{-H}$, $6'''\text{-H}$), 7.03 (1H, td, J 7.6, 1.1 Hz, $5''\text{-H}$), 7.11 (1H, tt, J 7.3, 1.1 Hz, $4'''\text{-H}$), 7.18 (1H, d, J 7.9 Hz, 6-H), 7.22 (1H, ddd, J 8.3, 7.6, 1.7 Hz, $4''\text{-H}$), 7.32–7.36 (2H, m, $3'''\text{-H}$, $5'''\text{-H}$), 7.39 (1H, dd, J 7.6, 1.7 Hz, $6''\text{-H}$), 7.43 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz, 3-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 21.0 (CH_3), 22.4 (COCH_3), 37.6 (C-1'), 80.1 (C-3'), 89.1 (C-2'), 115.4 (C-1''), 118.8 (C-2''', C-6'''), 118.8 (C-3''), 123.3 (C-4''), 123.3 (C-5''), 129.3 (C-5), 129.6 (C-4''), 129.8 (C-3''', C-5'''), 131.2 (C-6), 133.8 (C-6''), 133.9 (C-3), 137.7 (C-4), 140.5 (C-1), 157.3 (C-1'''), 157.7 (C-2''), 170.0 (CO). Invisible in the spectrum : C-2; MS (ESI, MeOH) m/z (%) : 434.1 (43) $[\text{M}(^{79}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$, 891.1 (100) $[\text{M}(^{79}\text{Br})+\text{M}(^{81}\text{Br})+\text{Na}]^+$. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{BrNO}_2$ (434.33) calcd. : 434.0750, found : 434.0751 $[\text{M}(^{79}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS); calcd. : 436.0731, found : 436.0735 $[\text{M}(^{81}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS).

N-(2-Bromo-4-fluorophenyl)-*N*-(3-(2-phenoxyphenyl)prop-2-yn-1-yl)acetamide (**4c**) :

A mixture of alkyne **12c** (164 mg, 608 μmol , 1.20 equiv.), **5a** (150 mg, 507 μmol , 1.00 equiv.), $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (29.3 mg, 25.3 μmol , 0.05 equiv.), CuI (9.65 mg, 50.6 μmol , 0.10 equiv.) and *n*- Bu_4NOAc (382 mg, 1.27 mmol, 2.50 equiv.) in 1,4-dioxane (5 mL) was treated according to GP1 for 1.5 h. CC (SiO_2 , PE/EtOAc 4/1) yielded the desired product (196 mg, 447 μmol , 88%) as a brown oil. TLC R_f 0.26 (PE/EtOAc 4/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 252 nm (4.234), 278 (3.539), 289 (3.562); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 1670, 1483, 1254, 1222, 1193, 860, 751, 690; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 1.78 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.97 (1H, d, J 17.5 Hz, $1'\text{-H}_a$), 5.33 (1H, d, J 17.5 Hz, $1'\text{-H}_b$), 6.74 (1H, ddd, J 8.8, 7.8, 2.9 Hz, 5-H), 6.85 (1H, dd, J 8.3, 1.1 Hz, $3''\text{-H}$), 6.93–6.99

(2H, m, $2'''\text{-H}$, $6'''\text{-H}$), 7.04 (1H, td, J 7.5, 1.1 Hz, $5''\text{-H}$), 7.13 (1H, tt, J 7.4, 1.2 Hz, $4'''\text{-H}$), 7.20–7.25 (1H, m, $4''\text{-H}$), 7.27–7.32 (1H, m, 6-H), 7.32–7.42 (4H, m, 3-H, $6''\text{-H}$, $3'''\text{-H}$, $5''\text{-H}$); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 22.4 (COCH_3), 37.6 (C-1'), 80.5 (C-3'), 88.6 (C-2'), 115.2 (C-1''), 115.7, (d, J 22 Hz, C-5), 118.7 (C-2''', C-6'''), 118.9 (C-3''), 120.8 (d, J 26 Hz, C-3), 123.4 (C-4'''), 123.4 (C-5''), 124.4, (d, J 10 Hz, C-2), 129.8 (C-4''), 129.9 (C-3''', C-5'''), 132.7 (d, J 9 Hz, C-6), 133.7 (C-6''), 136.7 (d, J 4 Hz, C-1), 157.2 (C-1'''), 157.7 (C-2''), 161.8 (d, J 253 Hz, C-4), 169.7 (CO). MS (ESI, MeOH) m/z (%) : 438.1 (36) $[\text{M}(^{79}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$, 460.0 (26) $[\text{M}(^{79}\text{Br})+\text{Na}]^+$, 899.1 (100) $[\text{M}(^{79}\text{Br})+\text{M}(^{81}\text{Br})+\text{Na}]^+$. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{17}\text{BrFNO}_2$ (438.30) calcd. : 438.0499, found : 438.0495 $[\text{M}(^{79}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS); calcd. : 440.0480, found : 440.0478 $[\text{M}(^{81}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS).

N-(3-(2-([1,1'-Biphenyl]-4-yloxy)phenyl)prop-2-yn-1-yl)-*N*-(2-bromo-4-methylphenyl)acetamide (**4d**) :

A mixture of alkyne **12b** (85.8 mg, 322 μmol , 1.20 equiv.), **5b** (100 mg, 269 μmol , 1.00 equiv.), $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (15.5 mg, 13.4 μmol , 0.05 equiv.), CuI (5.12 mg, 26.7 μmol , 0.10 equiv.) and *n*- Bu_4NOAc (203 mg, 672 μmol , 2.50 equiv.) in 1,4-dioxane was treated according to GP1 for 1 h. CC (SiO_2 , PE/EtOAc 6/1) yielded the desired product (135 mg, 264 μmol , 98%) as a yellow oil. TLC R_f 0.22 (PE/EtOAc 6/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 200 nm (4.951), 253 (4.474); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 1668, 1481, 1380, 1254, 1224, 838, 761, 697; ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 1.77 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.26 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.98 (1H, d, J 17.6 Hz, $1'\text{-H}_a$), 5.32 (1H, d, J 17.6 Hz, $1'\text{-H}_b$), 6.86 (1H, ddd, J 8.0, 1.3, 0.6 Hz, 5-H), 6.93 (1H, d, J 8.2 Hz, $3''\text{-H}$), 7.00–7.04 (2H, m, $3'''\text{-H}$, $5'''\text{-H}$), 7.06 (1H, td, J 7.5, 0.6 Hz, $5''\text{-H}$), 7.19 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, 6-H), 7.24–7.28 (1H, m, $4''\text{-H}$), 7.34

(1H, t, J 7.4 Hz, 4''''-H), 7.41–7.43 (2H, m, 3-H, 6''-H), 7.44 (2H, t, J 7.4 Hz, 3''''-H, 5''''-H), 7.54–7.59 (4H, m, 2'''-H, 6'''-H, 2''''-H, 6''''-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 20.9 (CH_3), 22.3 (COCH_3), 37.6 (C-1'), 80.0 (C-3'), 89.3 (C-2'), 115.6 (C-1''), 118.9 (C-3''', C-5'''), 119.2 (C-3''), 123.4 (C-2), 123.6 (C-5''), 127.0 (C-2''', C-6'''), 127.2 (C-4'''), 128.5 (C-2''', C-6'''), 129.0 (C-3''', C-5'''), 129.4 (C-5), 129.8 (C-4''), 131.2 (C-6), 133.9 (C-3), 133.9 (C-6''), 136.4 (C-1'''), 137.8 (C-4), 140.6 (C-1, C-1'''), 157.0 (C-4'''), 157.7 (C-2''), 170.1 (CO); MS (ESI, MeOH) m/z (%) : 512.1 (41) $[\text{M}^{(81}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$, 534.1 (18) $[\text{M}^{(81}\text{Br})+\text{Na}]^+$, 1038.2 (100) $[\text{M}^{(79}\text{Br})+\text{M}^{(81}\text{Br})+\text{NH}_4]^+$. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{24}\text{BrNO}_2$ (510.43) calcd. : 510.1063, found : 510.1063 $[\text{M}^{(79}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS); calcd. : 512.1044, found. : 512.1049 $[\text{M}^{(81}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$ (ESI HRMS).

N-(2-Bromo-4-fluorophenyl)-*N*-(3-(2-(4-(tertbutyl)phenoxy)phenyl)prop-2-yn-1-yl)acetamide (4e) :

A mixture of alkyne **12d** (92.0 mg, 365 μmol , 1.20 equiv.), **5c** (100 mg, 284 μmol , 1.00 equiv.), $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (16.4 mg, 14.2 μmol , 0.05 equiv.), CuI (5.41 mg, 28.4 μmol , 0.10 equiv.) and *n*- Bu_4NOAc (214 mg, 710 μmol , 2.50 equiv.) in 1,4-dioxane (3 mL) was treated according to GP1 for 1 h. CC (SiO_2 , PE/EtOAc 5/1) yielded the desired product (127 mg, 257 μmol , 90%) as a yellow solid. TLC R_f 0.33 (PE/EtOAc 5/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 252 nm (4.184), 289 (3.512); IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 2960, 1675, 1508, 1487, 1255, 1229, 860, 758; ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 1.33 (9H, s, $\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.78 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.97 (1H, d, J 17.6 Hz, 1'- H_a), 5.36 (1H, d, J 17.6 Hz, 1'- H_b), 6.66 (1H, ddd, J 8.7, 7.9, 2.9 Hz, 5-H), 6.84 (1H, d, J 8.3 Hz, 3''-H), 6.87–6.92 (2H, m, 2'''-H, 6'''-H), 7.01 (1H, td, J 7.6, 1.0 Hz, 5''-H), 7.22 (1H, ddd, J 8.3, 7.6, 1.7 Hz, 4''-H), 7.32–7.35 (2H, m, 3-H, 6-H), 7.35–7.39 (3H, m, 6''-H, 3'''-H, 5'''-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 22.3

(COCH_3), 31.7 ($\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 34.5 ($\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 37.5 (C-1'), 80.7 (C-3'), 88.4 (C-2'), 115.0 (C-1''), 115.8 (d, J 22 Hz, C-5), 118.4 (C-2''', C-6'''), 118.6 (C-3''), 120.8 (d, J 26 Hz, C-3), 123.1 (C-5''), 124.4 (d, J 10 Hz, C-2), 126.8 (C-3''', C-5'''), 129.8 (C-4''), 132.9 (d, J 10 Hz, C-6), 133.7 (C-6''), 136.7 (d, J 5 Hz, C-1), 146.6 (C-4'''), 154.9 (C-1'''), 158.3 (C-2''), 162.0 (d, J 253 Hz, C-4), 169.9 (CO); MS (ESI, MeOH) m/z (%) : 496.1 (16) $[\text{M}^{(81}\text{Br})+\text{H}]^+$, 516.1 (24) $[\text{M}^{(79}\text{Br})+\text{Na}]^+$, 1011.2 (100) $[\text{M}^{(79}\text{Br})+\text{M}^{(81}\text{Br})+\text{Na}]^+$. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{25}\text{BrFNO}_2$ (494.40) calcd. : 516.0945, found : 516.0943 $[\text{M}^{(79}\text{Br})+\text{Na}]^+$ (ESI HRMS); calcd. : 518.0926, found : 518.0926 $[\text{M}^{(81}\text{Br})+\text{Na}]^+$ (ESI HRMS).

1-(3-(9*H*-Xanthen-9-yl)-1*H*-indole-1-yl)ethan-1-one (**8a**) :

A mixture of amide **4a** (20.0 mg, 47.6 μmol , 1.00 equiv.), PPh_3 (12.4 mg, 47.6 μmol , 1.00 equiv.), K_2CO_3 (32.1 mg, 237 μmol , 5.00 equiv.) and $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$ (2.4 mg, 9.50 μmol , 0.20 equiv.) in DMF (1.8 mL) was treated according to GP2 for 2 h. Work up : sat. aq. NH_4Cl solution (5 mL), MTBE (3 $\times$ 20 mL). CC (SiO_2 , PE/ CH_2Cl_2 5/1) yielded the desired product (12.9 mg, 38.0 μmol , 80%) as a yellow solid. TLC R_f 0.22 (PE/MTBE 5/1); UV (CH_3CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ) : 238 nm (4.351), 281 (3.800), 290 (3.921), 299 (3.852); IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) : 2921, 1706, 1446, 1377, 1329, 1253, 1007, 933, 742; ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 2.61 (3H, s, COCH_3), 5.51 (1H, s, 9-H), 6.94 (2H, td, J 7.4, 1.3 Hz, 2-H, 7-H), 7.08–7.12 (3H, m, 1-H, 8-H, 5'-H), 7.16 (2H, dd, J 8.2, 1.3 Hz, 4-H, 5-H), 7.22 (2H, ddd, J 8.5, 6.8, 1.5 Hz, 3-H, 6-H), 7.27 (2H, ddd, J 7.4, 4.1, 2.7 Hz, 5'-H, 6'-H), 7.36 (1H, s, 7'-H), 8.40 (1H, s, 2'-H); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 24.1/29.8 (COCH_3), 35.5 (C-9), 116.6 (C-4, C-5, C-2'), 119.9 (C-6'), 122.5 (C-7'), 123.1 (C-5'), 123.2 (C-2, C-7), 123.5 (C-1a, C-8a), 125.2 (C-3'), 125.9 (C-3a'), 128.2 (C-3, C-6), 128.6 (C-1'), 129.1 (C-1, C-8), 136.4 (C-7a'), 151.0 (C-4a, C-5a), 168.3 (CO); MS (EI, MeOH) m/z (%) :

339.1 (61) [M]⁺, 296.1 (100) [M-C₂H₃O]⁺. C₂₃H₁₇NO₂ (339.12) calcd. : 339.1259, found : 339.1265 [M]⁺ (EI HRMS); calcd. : 362.1151, found : 362.1142 [M+Na]⁺ (ESI HRMS).

1-(5-Methyl-3-(9H-xanthen-9-yl)-1H-indole-1-yl)ethan-1-one (8b) :

Procedure according to GP2 : A mixture of alkyne **4b** (50.7 mg, 117 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), PPh₃ (30.6 mg, 117 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), K₂CO₃ (80.7 mg, 584 μmol, 5.00 equiv.) and Pd(OAc)₂ (5.24 mg, 23.3 μmol, 0.20 equiv.) in DMF (2.5 mL) was treated according to GP2 for 2 h. Work up : sat. aq. NH₄Cl solution (5 mL), H₂O (5 mL), MTBE (4 × 10 mL). CC (SiO₂, PE/CH₂Cl₂ 3/2→1/1→1/2) yielded the desired product (34.3 mg, 97.1 μmol, 83%) as a white solid.

Procedure according to GP3 : A mixture of alkyne **12c** (108 mg, 405 μmol, 1.20 equiv.), **5a** (100 mg, 338 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), PPh₃ (88.6 mg, 338 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), *n*-Bu₄NOAc (305 mg, 1.01 mmol, 3.00 equiv.) and Pd(OAc)₂ (15.2 mg, 67.5 μmol, 0.20 equiv.) in DMF (9 mL) was treated according to GP3. Work up : sat. aq. NH₄Cl solution (15 mL), H₂O (15 mL), MTBE (3 × 20 mL), brine (30 mL). CC (SiO₂, PE/CH₂Cl₂ 1/1) yielded the desired product (90.0 mg, 255 μmol, 75%) as a white solid. TLC *R*_f 0.24 (PE/CH₂Cl₂ 1/1); UV (CH₃CN) λ_{max} (lg ε) : 242 nm (4.424), 292 (3.971), 304 (3.967); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm⁻¹) : 1702, 1478, 1448, 1384, 1344, 1325, 1253, 753; ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 2.31 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.60 (3H, s, COCH₃), 5.50 (1H, s, 9-H), 6.96 (2H, td, *J* 7.4, 1.3 Hz, 2-H, 7-H), 7.08–7.09 (1H, m, 4'-H), 7.10–7.13 (3H, m, 1-H, 8-H, 6'-H), 7.17 (2H, dd, *J* 8.2, 1.3 Hz, 4-H, 5-H), 7.21–7.25 (2H, m, 3-H, 6-H), 7.28 (1H, s, 2'-H), 8.27 (1H, s_{br}, 7'-H); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 21.7 (CH₃), 24.2 (COCH₃), 35.5 (C-9), 116.4 (C-7'), 116.7 (C-4, C-5), 119.8 (C-4'), 122.9 (C-1a, C-8a), 123.4 (C-2, C-7), 123.5 (C-2'), 125.9 (C-7a'), 126.7 (C-6'), 128.3 (C-3, C-6), 129.0 (C-3a'),

129.2 (C-1, C-8), 133.2 (C-5'), 134.7 (C-3'), 151.3 (C-4a, C-5a), 168.3 (CO); MS (ESI, MeOH) *m/z* (%) : 376.1 (74) [M+Na]⁺, 729.3 (100) [2M+Na]⁺. C₂₄H₁₉NO₂ (353.42) calcd. : 354.1489, found : 354.1488 [M+H]⁺ (ESI HRMS); calcd. : 376.1308, found : 376.1305 [M+Na]⁺ (ESI HRMS).

1-(5-Fluoro-3-(9H-xanthen-9-yl)-1H-indole-1-yl)ethan-1-one (8c) :

Procedure according to GP2 : A mixture of alkyne **4c** (50.0 mg, 114 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), PPh₃ (29.9 mg, 114 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), K₂CO₃ (78.8 mg, 570 μmol, 5.00 equiv.) and Pd(OAc)₂ (5.12 mg, 22.8 μmol, 0.20 equiv.) in DMF (2.5 mL) was treated according to GP2 for 3 h. Work up : sat. aq. NH₄Cl solution (5 mL), H₂O (5 mL), MTBE (5 × 10 mL). CC (SiO₂, PE/CH₂Cl₂ 2/1) yielded the desired product (25.8 mg, 72.2 μmol, 63%) as a white solid.

Procedure according to GP3 : A mixture of alkyne **12c** (109 mg, 405 μmol, 1.20 equiv.), **5a** (100 mg, 338 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), PPh₃ (88.6 mg, 338 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), *n*-Bu₄NOAc (305 mg, 1.01 mmol, 3.00 equiv.) and Pd(OAc)₂ (15.2 mg, 67.5 μmol, 0.20 equiv.) in DMF (9 mL) was treated according to GP3. Work up : sat. aq. NH₄Cl solution (15 mL), H₂O (15 mL), MTBE (4 × 20 mL), brine (30 mL). CC (SiO₂, PE/CH₂Cl₂ 2/1→1/1) yielded the desired product (84.9 mg, 238 μmol, 70%) as a white solid. TLC *R*_f 0.16 (PE/CH₂Cl₂ 2/1); UV (CH₃CN) λ_{max} (lg ε) : 238 nm (4.377), 291 (4.071), 301 (4.045); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm⁻¹) : 1704, 1478, 1471, 1447, 1384, 1253, 945, 753; ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 2.63 (3H, s, COCH₃), 5.48 (1H, s, 9-H), 6.89 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0, 2.5 Hz, 4'-H), 6.97 (2H, td, *J* 7.5, 1.3 Hz, 2-H, 7-H), 6.97–7.01 (1H, m, 6'-H), 7.09 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, 1-H, 8-H), 7.18 (2H, dd, *J* 8.0, 1.3 Hz, 4-H, 5-H), 7.24 (2H, td, *J* 8.0, 1.5 Hz, 3-H, 6-H), 7.41 (1H, s, 2'-H), 8.38 (1H, s_{br}, 7'-H); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 24.0 (COCH₃), 35.6 (C-9), 105.8 (d, *J* 24 Hz,

C-4'), 113.2 (d, *J* 25 Hz, C-6'), 116.9 (C-4, C-5), 117.9 (d, *J* 11 Hz, C-7'), 122.2 (C-1a, C-8a), 123.4 (C-2, C-7), 124.6 (C-2'), 125.7 (d, *J* 5 Hz, C-7a'), 128.5 (C-3, C-6), 129.1 (C-1, C-8), 129.7 (d, *J* 10 Hz, C-3a'), 133.0 (C-3'), 151.2 (C-4a, C-5a), 159.4 (d, *J* 241 Hz, C-5'), 168.2 (CO); MS (ESI, MeOH) *m/z* (%): 358.1 (29) [M+H]⁺, 380.1 (63) [M+Na]⁺, 737.2 (100) [2M+Na]⁺. C₂₃H₁₆FNO₂ (357.38), calcd.: 358.1238, found: 358.1231 [M+H]⁺ (ESI HRMS); calcd.: 380.1057, found: 380.1052 [M+Na]⁺ (ESI HRMS).

1-(5-Methyl-3-(2-phenyl-9H-xanthen-9-yl)-1H-indole-1-yl)ethan-1-one (8d):

A mixture of alkyne **4d** (29.5 mg, 57.8 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), PPh₃ (15.1 mg, 57.8 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), K₂CO₃ (39.9 mg, 289 μmol, 5.00 equiv.) and Pd(OAc)₂ (2.60 mg, 11.6 μmol, 0.20 equiv.) in DMF (2.0 mL) was treated according to GP2 for 2 h. Work up: sat. aq. NH₄Cl solution (5 mL), H₂O (5 mL), MTBE (3 × 8 mL). CC (SiO₂, PE/CH₂Cl₂ 1/1) yielded the desired product **8d** (18.8 mg, 43.8 μmol, 76%) as a white solid. TLC *R_f* 0.32 (PE/CH₂Cl₂ 4/6); UV (CH₃CN) λ_{max} (lg ε): 245 nm (4.498), 266 (4.492), 303 (4.107); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm⁻¹): 3326, 1703, 1475, 1451, 1383, 1325, 1251, 759; ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 2.32 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.61 (3H, s, COCH₃), 5.55 (1H, s, 9-H), 6.97 (1H, ddd, *J* 8.4, 7.4, 1.2 Hz, 7-H), 7.11 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, 6'-H), 7.13–7.15 (2H, m, 4'-H, 8-H), 7.19 (1H, dd, *J* 8.2, 1.2 Hz, 5-H), 7.23–7.26 (2H, m, 4-H, 6-H), 7.27–7.29 (1H, m, 4''-H), 7.33 (1H, dd, *J* 2.2, 0.7 Hz, 1-H), 7.34–7.37 (2H, m, 3''-H, 5''-H), 7.40–7.44 (2H, m, 2''-H, 6''-H), 7.47 (1H, ddd, *J* 8.5, 2.2, 0.6 Hz, 3-H), 8.26 (1H, s, 7'-H). Invisible in the spectrum: 2'-H; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 21.7 (CH₃), 24.3 (COCH₃), 35.7 (C-9), 116.4 (C-7'), 116.7 (C-5), 117.1 (C-4), 119.8 (C-4'), 122.7 (C-8a), 123.0 (C-1a), 123.4 (C-2'), 123.4 (C-7), 126.0 (C-7a'), 126.8 (C-6'), 126.9 (C-2'', C-6''), 127.1 (C-3), 127.1 (C-4''), 127.9 (C-1), 128.3 (C-6), 128.8 (C-3'', C-5''), 129.3 (C-8), 133.2 (C-5'), 134.8

(C-3'), 136.5 (C-2), 140.4 (C-1''), 150.8 (C-4a), 151.2 (C-5a), 168.3 (CO). Invisible in the spectrum: C-3a'; MS (ESI, MeOH) *m/z* (%): 452.2 (77) [M+Na]⁺. C₃₀H₂₃NO₂ (429.52) calcd.: 452.1621, found: 452.1620 [M+Na]⁺ (ESI HRMS).

1-(3-(2-(tert-Butyl)-9H-xanthen-9-yl)-5-fluoro-1H-indole-1-yl)ethan-1-one (8e):

Procedure according to GP2: A mixture of alkyne **4e** (50.0 mg, 101 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), PPh₃ (26.5 mg, 101 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), K₂CO₃ (69.9 mg, 506 μmol, 5.00 equiv.) and Pd(OAc)₂ (4.54 mg, 20.2 μmol, 0.20 equiv.) in DMF (2.5 mL) was treated according to GP2 for 2 h. Work up: sat. aq. NH₄Cl solution (5 mL), H₂O (5 mL), MTBE (3 × 10 mL). CC (SiO₂, PE/CH₂Cl₂ 1/1) yielded the desired product **8e** (33.0 mg, 79.8 μmol, 79%) as a brown solid.

Procedure according to GP3: A mixture of alkyne **12c** (92.0 mg, 341 μmol, 1.20 equiv.), **5b** (100 mg, 284 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), PPh₃ (74.5 mg, 284 μmol, 1.00 equiv.), *n*-Bu₄NOAc (257 mg, 852 μmol, 3.00 equiv.) and Pd(OAc)₂ (12.8 mg, 56.8 μmol, 0.20 equiv.) in DMF (8 mL) was treated according to GP3. Work up: sat. aq. NH₄Cl solution (15 mL), H₂O (15 mL), MTBE (4 × 20 mL), brine (30 mL). CC (SiO₂, PE/CH₂Cl₂ 2/1→1/1) yielded the desired product (81.4 mg, 197 μmol, 69%) as a brown solid. TLC *R_f* 0.26 (PE/CH₂Cl₂ 1/1); UV (CH₃CN) λ_{max} (lg ε): 240 nm (4.427), 291 (4.087), 301 (4.071); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm⁻¹): 2961, 1704, 1481, 1470, 1446, 1383, 1252, 944; ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 1.20 (9H, s, C(CH₃)₃), 2.61 (3H, s, COCH₃), 5.45 (1H, s, 9-H), 6.96 (1H, td, *J* 7.7, 1.3 Hz, 7-H), 6.98–7.02 (2H, m, 4'-H, 6'-H), 7.10–7.13 (3H, m, 1-H, 4-H, 8-H), 7.16 (1H, dd, *J* 8.1, 1.3 Hz, 5-H), 7.23 (1H, tdd, *J* 7.7, 1.6, 0.4 Hz, 6-H), 7.26–7.29 (1H, m, 3-H), 7.31 (1H, s, 2'-H), 8.37 (1H, s_{br}, 7'-H); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 24.1 (COCH₃), 31.6 (C(CH₃)₃), 34.5 (C(CH₃)₃), 36.1 (C-9), 105.7 (d, *J* 24 Hz, C-4'),

113.1 (d, J 25 Hz, C-6'), 116.3 (C-4), 116.8 (C-5), 117.8 (d, J 11 Hz, C-7'), 121.6 (C-1a), 122.7 (C-8a), 123.3 (C-7), 124.4 (C-2'), 125.6 (C-3), 125.7 (C-1), 126.3 (d, J 5 Hz, C-7a'), 128.4 (C-6), 129.1 (C-8), 129.8 (d, J 10 Hz, C-3a'), 132.9 (C-3'), 146.3 (C-2), 149.2 (C-4a'), 151.6 (C-5a'), 159.4 (d, J 240 Hz, C-5'), 168.2 (CO); MS (ESI, MeOH) m/z (%): 414.2 (66) $[M+H]^+$, 849.4 (100) $[2M+Na]^+$. $C_{27}H_{24}FNO_2$ (413.49), calcd.: 414.1864, found: 414.1863 $[M+H]^+$ (ESI HRMS) calcd.: 436.1683, found: 436.1675 $[M+Na]^+$ (ESI HRMS).

5-Fluoro-3-(9H-xanthen-9-yl)-1H-indole (15) :

A solution of **8c** (15.7 mg, 43.9 μ mol, 1.00 equiv.) and KOH (12.3 mg, 219 μ mol, 5.00 equiv.) in THF (1.6 mL) and H₂O (0.5 mL) was stirred at 40 °C for 5 h. After removal of the solvent *in vacuo*, the residue was purified by flash CC (PE/MTBE 3/1) to yield the desired product (13.0 mg, 41.3 μ mol, 94%) as a light purple solid. TLC R_f 0.24 (PE/MTBE 3/1); IR (ATR) $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm⁻¹): 1575, 1477, 1446, 1251, 1093, 934, 901, 748, 736, 595; UV (CH₃CN) λ_{max} (lg ϵ): 243 nm (4.112), 287 (3.900); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 5.48 (1H, s, 9'-H), 6.85 (1H, td, J 9.0, 2.5 Hz, 6-H), 6.90–6.96 (3H, m, 4-H, 2'-H, 7'-H), 7.07 (2H, d, J 7.7 Hz, 1'-H, 8'-H), 7.12–7.15 (3H, m, 2-H, 4'-H, 5'-H), 7.18 (2H, ddd, J 8.5, 6.9, 1.6 Hz, 3'-H, 6'-H), 7.22 (1H, dd, J 8.8, 4.4 Hz, 7-H), 8.00 (1H, s_{br}, NH); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 35.5 (C-9'), 104.5/104.7 (d, J 23.4 Hz, C-4), 110.5/110.7 (d, J 25.1 Hz, C-6), 111.7/111.8 (d, J 9.6 Hz, C-7), 116.4 (C-4', C-5'), 120.5/120.6 (d, J 4.6 Hz, C-3), 123.1 (C-2', C-7'), 123.9 (C-1a', C-8a'), 124.4 (C-2), 126.0/126.1 (d, J 10.2 Hz, C-3a), 127.8 (C-3', C-6'), 129.3 (C-1', C-8'), 133.3 (C-7a), 151.3 (C-4a', C-5a'), 156.7/158.5 (d, J 236 Hz, C-5); MS (EI, MeOH) m/z (%): 315.1 (100) $[M]^+$, 314.1 (99) $[M-H]^+$, 181.1 (30) $[M-C_8H_4FNH]^+$. $C_{21}H_{14}FNO$ (315.34) calcd.: 315.1059, found: 315.1058 $[M]^+$ (EI HRMS); calcd.: 314.0981, found: 314.0980 $[M-H]^+$ (EI HRMS).

X-Ray diffraction experiments : Suitable single crystals for X-ray structural analysis of **8b** were obtained by slow evaporation of the corresponding ethanol solution, and a single crystal was mounted with inert oil^{22a,b} on a MiTeGen-Loop. The diffraction data were collected from the shock-cooled crystals at 100(2) K on a Bruker D8 three circle diffractometer equipped with a SMART APEX II CCD detector and a Mo rotating anode with INCOATEC Quazar mirror optics ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å). The data were integrated with SAINT^{22c} and an analytical absorption correction with SADABS^{22d} was applied. The structures were solved by direct methods (SHELXS-97)^{22e} and refined against all data by full-matrix least-squares methods on F^2 (SHELXL-2012)^{22e} within the SHELXLE GUI^{22f}. All non-hydrogen-atoms were refined with anisotropic displacement parameters. The hydrogen atoms were refined isotropically on calculated positions using a riding model with their U_{iso} values constrained to 1.5 U_{eq} of their pivot atoms for terminal sp³ carbon atoms and 1.2 times for all other carbon atoms.

Crystal data for 8b : $M_r = 353.40$, $0.348 \times 0.096 \times 0.054$ mm³, monoclinic, $P2_1/n$, $a = 6.393(2)$ Å, $b = 26.264(3)$ Å, $c = 10.740(2)$ Å, $V = 11.0(7)$ Å³, $\alpha = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 92.95(2)^\circ$, $Z = 4$, $\rho_{calc} = 1.303$ Mg/m³, $T = 100(2)$ K, $\mu(Mo K\alpha) = 0.083$ mm⁻¹, $2\theta_{max} = 59.146^\circ$, 41195 reflections measured, 5024 independent ($R_{int} = 0.0242$, $R1 = 0.0414$ ($I > 2\sigma(I)$), $wR2 = 0.1144$ (all data), res. density peaks : 0.390 and -0.192 eÅ⁻³).

Deposition number CCDC-948415 for compound No. **8b**. Free copies of the data can be obtained via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html> (or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : 44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

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